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NARRATIVE REVIEW ON INSIGHTS OF OPHTHALMIC DRUG DELIVERY BY USING CONTACT LENSES

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ABSTRACT

In ocular drug delivery system (ODDS) majority of medications are delivered as eye drops and these may reduce the intraocular pressure but having major deficiencies like low patient compliance and low bioavailability. Therefore, ophthalmic drug delivery has become very fashionable with their distinctive benefits like extended drug release and more than 50% bioavailability. To achieve controlled and sustained drug deliveries from contact lenses, we tend to come that numerous techniques like compounding into nanoparticles, micelle, liposomes have many technologies in developing the load of a drug connected lenses like soaking, molecular acquisition, defense of drug loaded mixture nanoparticles, ion ligand polymeric system. Some of the major disadvantages to this technology are corneal problems, conjunctivitis etc. The rate of drug delivery is not constant overtime with the bulk of medicine within the lens being delivered within the initial stage rather that at end of treatment period.

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INTRODUCTION

Contact lenses (CLs) are small, round, curved, thin transparent piece of correctional lenses that can put directly over the cornea of eyes to improve sight, instead of wearing glasses these lens floats on a film of tears. Contact lenses can be used for ophthalmic drug delivery in progress of the field by contact lenses drug delivery system has been established recently with controlled loading and sustained release, due to their unique advantages like extended wear, more than 50% bioavailability. To achieve controlled and sustained drug delivery from contact lenses, researchers are working on various systems like polymeric nanoparticles, microemulsion, micelle, liposomes, use of vitamin E etc. Scientists are working on different areas of therapeutic contact lenses to treat ocular diseases by implementing techniques like soaking method, molecular imprinting, entrapment of drug-loaded colloidal nanoparticles and supercritical fluid technology as shown in Fig 1. In various critical properties such as water content, tensile strength, ion permeability, transparency and oxygen permeability limit the commercialization of therapeutic contact lenses also issues in drug stability during drug release in storage and packaging solutions like protein adherence, shelf life study, cost benefit analysis are still to be addressed. This newer technology can be used for treatment of various ocular diseases like glaucoma, cataract and other retinal diseases¹.

Fig 1: Thin transparent piece of correctional lenses that can put directly over the cornea of eyes to improve sight.

The utilization of CLs for visual medication conveyance conquers a few of the obstructions that limit in powerful utilization of eye drops. The arrangement of a CL on the cornea isolates the attack pre-focal point (presented to the outside condition) and post-focal point (between the focal point and cornea) compartments, with the post-focal point compartment being exceptionally compelling because of restricted tear blending and trade. Thus, drugs discharged from the CL into this compartment possibly have a drawn-out contact time with the cornea, prompting improved bioavailability. Over half of the medications discharged from a CL can diffuse into the cornea, which is something like multiple times more effective than eye drops. This expansion in productivity allows considerably diminished fixations to be utilized in diminishing the potential for reactions as less medication is assimilated fundamentally. Another favorable position to utilizing a CL as a medication drug delivery stage is the capacity to convey tranquilizes over broadened timeframes, which takes out the requirement for different dosing. For visual contaminations, for example, microbial keratitis, eye drop applications can be as incessant as applications consistently. This can be exceptionally troublesome for patients, particularly amid rest, and extreme diseases regularly lead to hospitalization, absolutely to guarantee proper medication organization. Contact focal points successfully fill in as a medication store and discharge the medication over a set time span. In a perfect circumstance, the objective medication frames a collaboration with the CL polymer and separates from the focal point arrange in a period subordinate way into the post-focal point tear film, for inevitable ingestion by the visual tissues²⁻⁴.

Although using contact lenses have various benefits but there are many problems to face in lens hygiene regimes can be difficult to follow. It also reasonably good eye hand coordination for insertion and removal of the contact lenses. CL's have bigger risk of infections, scratches and injuries to the cornea. There is high possibility of allergic reactions to CL cleaning solutions but in sometimes it may lead to corneal irritation and conjunctivitis. Protein deposits can build upon the CLs in rubbing of eyes may cause the lens to fall off. The lens can stick to the eye ball because of moisture⁵.

FACTORS AFFECTING DRUG DELIVERY TRANSPARENCY OF THE LENS

Transparency of the defined contact focal point is a key factor influencing drug delivery and can't be undermined because of the joining of medication particles or added substances. The epic methodologies have empowered to detail and join materials in contact focal points which exhibited great straightforwardness as appeared in Fig 2. For example, contact focal points defined with cutting edge procedures, for example, atomic engraving and supercritical dissolvable methodologies, stacked liposomes, and microemulsions showed great straightforwardness⁶.

Fig 2: Transparency of the formulated contact lens is a key factor affecting the drug delivery

OXYGEN PERMEABILITY

The human eye does not get satisfactory bloodstream to supply the eye with enough oxygen to expel enough carbon dioxide. It, for the most part, depends on its introduction to the air for oxygen supply. Consequently, the readied focal points ought to enable the free exchange of oxygen to the eyes and low oxygen exchange inevitably causes extreme reactions. Looking to improve delicate contact focal point penetrability researcher began to make hydrogels from silicone-based polymers like polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS). Notwithstanding, so as to keep away from hypoxia, an all-inclusive wearable contact focal point must furnish in any event simple to achieve with customary hydrophilic contact focal point and different scientists have utilized these all-inclusive wears contact focal points for ophthalmic medication conveyance with no impact on the oxygen porousness of the focal point⁷⁻⁹.

WET ABILITY

Hydrophobic polymers will repulse the water that makes up a larger part of the tear surface. This upsets the tear stream and results in the affidavit of an egg whites' film on the focal point, which in the end lessens the viability of the contact and can cause contamination or potentially disturbance. Along these lines, if a contact focal point surface is exceedingly hydrophobic it should be made hydrophilic. Doping the polymer or treating the outside of the polymer can do this adjustment in the morphology of the surface. There are reports in the writing which propose that supercritical liquid-based contact focal points keep their wet capacity properties in the wake of handling. Notwithstanding wet capacity and substance, the solace of a delicate contact focal point additionally relies upon the viscoelasticity of the system and on its sliding over the eye surface and the tops¹⁰⁻¹¹.

WATER CONTENT

The permeability of the lens is proportional to the amount of water in the lens. As the percent weight of water increases in the lens, the permeability increases linearly. The ability of lenses to absorb large amounts of water also makes them highly hydrophilic. These attributes gives soft contact lenses the ability to achieve greater permeability and could be used for extended wear without disturbing the eye. However, achieving greater permeability is a complex issue as increase in water content will eventually lose the polymer strength. This can lead to tearing or scratching of the lens. A softer lens also offers the cornea less protection. Lenses with higher water content absorb more water-soluble drug compounds and releases it later into the tear film than do low water content lenses. Several drug retention strategies have been pursued to minimize the need for repeated treatments, especially in chronic diseases. They comprise viscosity-enhancing polymers, "in situ" gels undergoing phase transition from liquid to gel under physiological conditions, mucoadhesive and mucus-covered mucosal epithelial membranes, and nanoparticles drug-delivery systems as submicron structures in which drugs can be attached or encapsulated¹².

BARRIERS IN DIFFUSION AND PRODUCTIVE ABSORPTION OF TOPICALLY APPLIED DRUGS

There are a few physiological hindrances in dispersion and beneficial retention of topically connected medications in the pre-corneal and corneal spaces. The pre-corneal limitations in charge of poor visual bioavailability of customary ophthalmic measurement shapes are arrangement waste, lacrimation, tear weakening, tear turnover and conjunctival assimilation as spoke to in Fig.3. The medication unabsorbed by the cornea is either consumed by the conjunctiva or courses through the upper and the lower canaliculi into the lacrimal sac. The conjunctiva has a generally substantial surface territory, about multiple times the outside of cornea making the misfortune huge. Then again, tears weaken the rest of the medication in the circular drive which in this way decreases the trans-corneal transition. The medication substance, pH, tonicity of the measurements frames just as plan adjuvants can animate tear generation which may in the long run weaken the definition¹³⁻¹⁴.

Fig.3: Restrictions responsible for poor ocular bioavailability of conventional ophthalmic dosage forms.

THERMO-SET POLYMER HYDROGELS IN OCULAR CONTACT LENSES

The most popular type of ophthalmic lens is soft contact lens made of thermo-set polymer hydrogels. These gels possess three dimensional, amorphous networks with cross-links, similar to hard contact lens polymers, and are typically produced by cast molding or spin cast method. The reason for the softness of the lens is principally because these polymers exist above its glass transition temperature. Usually hydrogels are incorporated to compensate the hydrophobicity in lens surface remains hydrophobic as shown Fig 4. Hence, the lens surface is generally modified by plasma treatments which can alter the hydrophobic nature of the lens. On the other hand, few lens types have incorporated internal rewetting agents to ensure the hydrophilicity of the lens surface. A third process uses longer backbone polymer chains that results in less cross linking and increased wetting without surface alterations¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

Fig 4: longer backbone polymer chains that results in less cross linking and increased wetting.

APPROACHES FOR DRUG INCORPORATION

This have been used to incorporate drugs into contact lenses in loading drugs into preformed lenses with the drugs entrapped inside. Attempts were also made by dissolving drug in the monomer solution and followed polymerization, incorporation of drug loaded nano or micro based vesicular systems into the matrix, ocular inserts, ion exchange reaction with hydrogel functional groups etc. However, these techniques increase the number of processing step and are tedious for fabrication.

ELUCIVE TREATMENT AND THERAPRUTIC EFFICIANCY IN CONTACT LENSES

The success of ocular delivery using contact lenses is based on its ability to release the drug at controlled rate for an extended period of time. Traditionally, contact lens are applied by soaking it on a drug solution for a short duration and placed over the eye surface. However, the therapeutic efficiency of the commercial contact lens was not very successful and the treatment remains elusive. The major cause for this is due to the very low uptake of drug by the lens and the rapid release which eventually leads to low residence time as represented in Fig.5 Key limitations of soaking methods are the diffusion of water into the polymer and drug aqueous solubility. At present, the modern manufacturing techniques could be utilized to formulate extended wear contact lens (using silicone hydrogel) which are permeable to oxygen and can be worn for long duration¹⁸.

Fig.5: soaking methods are the diffusion of water into the polymer and drug aqueous solubility.

FOR CONTROLLED DRUG DELIVERY

Cyclodextrins (CDs) are cyclic oligosaccharides with hydrophobic cavity and form inclusion complex with several drug moieties through reversible non-covalent interaction, and have shown success in Ocular drug delivery system (ODDS). The activity of CDs in liquid formulations is limited as the de-complexation is instantaneous and however, in a polymeric network the release of the drug is controlled by forming the inclusion complexes and drug efficiently in their release could be sustained for several days. In addition, p-HEMA hydrogels were prepared by copolymerization with glycidyl methacrylate at various proportions and then beta-cyclodextrin (β -CD) was grafted to the network by reaction with the glycidyl groups under mild conditions. These results show that the hydrogels with pendant cyclodextrins are particularly useful for the development in soft contact lenses as they do not significantly alter swelling, optical transparency or oxygen permeability of the network with increase in drug load¹⁹.

PROBABILITY OF SYSTEMIC ABSORPTION USING CONTACT LENSES MODIFIED MEDICATED CONTACT LENSES

Molecular diffusion is the primary medication discharge component from the polymeric lattice that comprises the CL. One of the conceivable techniques to delay medicate discharge in CLs is to make a hindrance to plot the CL lattice which backs off medication dispersion, in this way drawing out its activity. Be that as it may, the production of these obstructions on the outside of the CLs is muddled because of the straightforwardness and oxygen saturation necessities. On the other hand, nutrient E (VE) CLs have been created for continued arrival of a few medications for ophthalmic use as appeared in Fig 6. Among the different medications tried timolol, one of the medications of decision for the treatment of glaucoma. This medication was picked because of its capability to cause extreme heart and pneumonic symptoms, for example, cardiovascular arrhythmias and bronchospasms, when assimilated into the fundamental flow. There is thusly an expanded advantage of utilizing CLs, since this strategy keeps up a steady medication fixation on the corneal surface and along these lines lessens the likelihood of foundational ingestion. Different sorts of CLs were tried with the expansion of VE and timolol at the same time amid a generation of the focal point²⁰⁻²¹.

Fig.6: CL matrix which slows down drug diffusion, therefore prolonging its action.

Furthermore, the use of CLs in only one eye had no effect in the untreated eye, indicating a decrease in systemic absorption of timolol in which case it is extremely important. VE also has the advantage of acting as a powerful antioxidant and is thus useful for the prevention of several ocular pathologies and also in enhancing the stability of susceptible drugs. Additionally, it protects the cornea against UV radiation and its aggregates do not interfere with the transparency of the CLs and the visual performance, since they are smaller than the wavelength size of visible light.

MEDICATED CONTACT LENSES WITH NANOPARTICLES

This strategy is based on the ability of nanoparticles (such as liposomes, polymeric nanoparticles and nanosized micelles) to include several drugs and control their release within CLs. Nanoparticles are complex colloidal systems of any shape with dimensions in the nanometer scale. These CLs possess nanoparticles incorporated during the production stage, thus ensuring a high concentration in the polymeric matrix, resulting in a high drug loading capacity as represented in Fig 7. Several nanoparticle types have been studied, including lipid nanoparticles, (liposomes, microemulsions, and micelles) and polymeric nanoparticles which comprise several biodegradable and non-biodegradable molecules²²⁻²³.

Fig 7: CLs possess nanoparticles incorporated during the production stage, thus ensuring a high concentration in the polymeric matrix, resulting in a high drug loading capacity.

LIPID-BASED NANOPARTICLES

The utilization of lipid nanostructures, for example, smaller scale emulsions and liposomes for medication fuse inside the CL lattice is particularly encouraging because of their thermodynamic soundness, which prompts a high medication stacking limit. Likewise, they consider the consideration of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic medications, in this way indicating extraordinary adaptability. It is anyway important to control the measure of nanoparticles caught in the CL lattice to such an extent that it has an expansive stacking limit without bargaining the straightforwardness of the focal point. It was discovered that these CLs advance medication discharge for as long as 8 days. With regards to glaucoma treatment, ponders are principally centered around the utilization of miniaturized scale emulsions. The utilization of micelles has so far exhibited to be significantly more encouraging. In any case, for surfactants to be conceivably utilized, it is basic to consider the parcel coefficient of the medication in the micelle. The segment coefficient is the fixation proportion of medication in two immiscible stages, one of the hydrophilic and the other hydrophobic.

This coefficient relies upon the hydrophobicity of the medication and the micellar center. It has been seen that if the segment coefficient is excessively low, the medication is quickly discharged from the micelle. The set number of concentrates to date on the utilization of these Nano systems for medication conveyance by CLs, including the utilization of other lipid-based particles, for example, nanostructured lipid bearers and strong lipid nano-frameworks, is generally because of different constraints regarding physical solidness, and the need to protect the CLs in a soaked medication arrangement so as to keep its untimely discharge, which prompts wastage of a lot of medication²⁴.

SUSTAINED DRUG RELEASE BY CONTACT LENSES FOR GLAUCOMA TREATMENT

The appearance of contact lenses (CLs) for vision correction has enabled the possibility of achieving a controlled and sustained drug release in the eye without the risk of compromising the optical performance. CLs are curved plastic discs, which adheres to the corneal tear film due to their surface tension. They can be used to correct vision problems for cosmetic and therapeutic purposes. Practically since the development of CLs, several studies have demonstrated that they can be suitable drug delivery systems for the treatment of several chronic and acute eye disorders. Therapeutic CLs consist of soft lenses formed by p-HEMA polymeric matrices with or without silicone, impregnated with drugs through various techniques like soaking in a solution with the drug, molecular imprinting, ion-ligands or microemulsion-loaded gels. These systems mechanism of action includes drug diffusion into the post-lens tear film followed by dispersion in the tear fluid and subsequent absorption by the cornea. Due to the constant absorption of the drug through the cornea, the concentration of the post-lens tear fluid remains lower than its concentration in the CLs, creating a constant and prolonged drug flow from the CLs to the cornea as represented in Fig 8. This is called the sink effect and this method results in an increased retention of the drug on the surface of the cornea (about 30 minutes) as opposed to around 2 minutes for eye drops and a bioavailability equal to or greater than 50%. In fact, it leads to an increased therapeutic efficacy, a reduction of drug fluctuations and a decrease in the amount of drug administered. Furthermore, CLs reduce the need for the addition of permeation enhancers and preservatives commonly used in multi-dose eye drops, which may cause ocular irritation²⁵⁻²⁶.

Fig.8: constant absorption of the drug through the cornea, the concentration of the post-lens tear fluid remains lower than its concentration in the CLs.

The benefits provided using CLs therefore enable their use for the treatment of various ophthalmic chronic diseases that require a constant therapeutic level of drug in the eye for an effective control of the disease, as is the case of glaucoma.

GENERATING CLs BASED DRUG CONTROLLED RELEASE SYSTEMS AND CLINICAL APPLICATIONS

The three main objectives underlying the development of DCRS based on CLs to enhance effective drug delivery are:

- To improve and extend CL wear tolerance by incorporating anti dry eye and allergy agents' formulations.
- To enhance patient compliance and reduce unwanted systemic side effects especially in chronic diseases such as glaucoma and dry eye whilst correcting ametropia.
- To manage corneal wound healing such as "bandage lenses" by incorporating antimicrobial or anti-inflammatory agents.

GLUCOMA TREATMENT WITH DRUG RELEASING LENSES

The researchers created contact lenses equipped with a drug-polymer film along the edge of the lens that slowly dispenses latanoprost—a drug usually prescribed for glaucoma patients—onto the surface of the eye. Because the drug film is on the edge, the center of the lens is clear, allowing for everything you would expect from a good contact lens, and eliminating much of the hassle associated with using eye drops. According to the researchers, contact lenses with lower dose films delivered the same amount of eye pressure reduction as standard latanoprost drops, while lenses delivering higher doses offered better pressure reduction than the drops. For glaucoma patients unhappy with their eye drops, that is good news. However, before this type of contact lens hits the market, more research is needed to confirm the safety and effectiveness of this therapy²⁷.

GLAUCOMA PROGRESSION WITH CONTACT LENSES

Glaucoma patients and their doctors have long wished that there was a way to see how the disease was changing the eye in time to react before too much damage was done. Current methods often make it difficult to get ahead of the disease, but now, researchers may have developed a way to do just that with a “smart” contact lens that can detect pressure changes inside the eye in real time. This means faster and more accurate assessments for glaucoma patients. Here’s how it works: A sensor detects changes in the curve of the eye. As eye pressure changes, the curve changes, generating an electrical signal sent to a wireless device that records the signals. The profile of signals indirectly shows eye pressure changes over time, which is linked to progression of the disease.

This real-time data represents a significant advantage over what we have today. Patients would have a better understanding of their disease, and their doctors would be able to better tailor treatments to their needs because they would be able to see more quickly whether a new medication is working for their patient. With financial support, these new and exciting contact lens technologies could make it easier for patients to comply with their medication plans and monitor both the progress of the disease and the efficacy of newly prescribed drugs. In time, researchers may even find a way to combine these two new technologies to create a single convenient device, capable of performing both drug delivery and pressure tests. Vitamin E aggregates incorporated within SHCLs block UV radiation and create a hydrophobic diffusion barrier to rapid drug diffusion without compromising proper oxygen permeability, ion permeability, and light refractive properties. Vitamin E loading proved to be very effective in increasing release duration of lidocaine, CyA, timolol, levofloxacin, chlorhexidine, dorzolamine, dexpantenol, betaine, dexamethasone and betamethasone, from hours to several days. Research on dry eye management has been increasingly focusing on the inflammatory aspect and CyA was FDA approved to treat moderate-to-severe dry eye disease. SHCLs were able to keep CyA delivery rates within therapeutic levels for 14 days. Vitamin E loaded CLs provided a CyA extended release up to one month²⁸.

ACCEPTANCE - CAN IT REACH CLINICIANS AND AFTER CLINICAL PRACTICE

From a logical and clinical angle, sedate conveying CLs could upset the manner in which visual sicknesses are dealt with. In any case, there is a fundamental concern whether this treatment stage will be promptly acknowledged by patients and clinicians alike. Considering that CL dropout is as of now a squeezing issue for the CL business, it might be hard to persuade a non-CL wearer to wear CLs, not to mention wear it for broadened periods. Nonetheless, the CL advertise is not little, with roughly 140 million current CL wearers worldwide that could profit by utilizing this innovation, should the need emerge for restorative intercession. Likewise, numerous exhibition wearers who experience refractive medical procedure can wear a gauze focal point for a brief timeframe, showing the potential momentary achievement of a remedial focal point to treat infection. The greater expense of utilizing a medication conveying CL contrasted with eye drops may likewise be a hindrance, in this way putting the onus on the endorsing professional to be a supporter of the innovation to such an extent that the temperance’s of the treatment methodology can be properly imparted. Of conclusive concern is that the patient populace for this innovation may not be the most suitable for specific illnesses (for instance glaucoma and constant fiery ailments), as they are frequently older, for whom the commonness of CL wear is now poor because of focal point bigotry and issues with CL inclusion and expulsion, giving another potential boundary²⁹.

CLINICAL INVESTIGATIONS

Several studies in human have been conducted to evaluate the novel contact lenses. In one attempt, Busin and Spitznas have assessed the activity of hydrogel bandage contact lenses (61% HEMA and 38.6% water content) soaked overnight in commercially available sterile gentamicin solution (0.5%) and placed on eyes of healthy adult volunteers. The results indicated greater (>minimum inhibitory concentration) and extended release (~3 days) of drug in the corneal region. In another study, 466 patients having cataract were given chloromycetin, gentamicin or carbenicilli subconjunctivally. Bausch and Lomb Clinical Research conducted 27 controlled extended wear clinical trials using Pure Vision lenses manufactured from a highly oxygen permeable, low water content (36%), surface treated silicone hydrogel material, balafilcon A for the presence of microbial keratitis. In Boston, a prototype two layers contact lens has been designed using PLGA and p-HEMA has been found to release the drug for more than 50 days, when tested in humans. Studies on the long term effects of the extended wear of senofilcon A silicone hydrogel contact lenses on ocular tissues has reported excellent biocompatibility and ocular tissue tolerance. Moreover, several studies in humans are undergoing at various research centers to ensure the efficiency, safety, biocompatibility and better patient compliance of the newly fabricated contact lenses³⁰.

FUTURE BARRIERS –FINE TUNING DRUG RELEASE CHARACTERISTICS

Although the issue of broadened medication discharge has been mostly settled with the advancement of novel CL materials, the energy is a long way from ideal. As of now, sedate discharge from these materials has been basically dispersion controlled and first-request energy are normally watched. Accordingly, the rate of medication discharge isn't steady after some time, with most of the medication inside the focal point being conveyed in the underlying stages as opposed to toward the finish of the treatment time frame. In this way, it will be hard to plan treatments when the medication portion can't be controlled for a time point. One potential answer for this issue is to utilize the CLs just for the length in which the discharge energy are zero-request and therefore a straight, unsurprising medication discharge rate. Be that as it may, this isn't an ideal arrangement, as it would require visit focal point substitution at timespans which might be awkward for the patient, thus advancement of CL materials equipped for zero-request discharge energy at unequaled periods is yet favored.

Beside the advancement of the 'perfect' medicate conveyance gadget, different issues are additionally deserving of notice. Anti-infection obstruction among visual pathogens, because of abuse and abuse of topical anti-infection agents in the eye, ill-advised dosing routine, and expanded span of treatment, is winding up progressively predominant. All things considered, ceaseless arrival of antimicrobials from a CL brings worries up with respect to microbial opposition. A noteworthy constraint in this field presently is a deficiency of in vivo examinations to approve the adequacy of a CL-conveyance stage. As far as anyone is concerned, there have just been two distributed creature considers utilizing CLs to treat a visual condition, the two of which uncovered that CLs give better bioavailability and diminished foundational medicate take-up contrasted with regular eye drop treatment. Further in vivo research is expected to help encourage this innovation into the clinical preliminary stage, and lead to the advancement of a suitable business item.

CONCLUSION

The contact lenses are upcoming novel technology in Ocular drug delivery (ODDS). Contact lenses have their importance in the world of cosmetic and Pharmaceutical technologies. They are in the developing stage in the field of therapeutic drug delivery. Several techniques have been developed for formulation the contact lenses like soaking particle in laden contact lenses, molecular imprinting and ion ligands. Research has also been going on to incorporate drugs like timolol, latanoprost in innovative ideas into contact lenses to treat the glaucoma as contact lenses in insufficient to till now and much research have been carried with more efforts and are needed to make this novel concept to the research market.

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